

Effectiveness of three different deep caries removal strategies in primary teeth: A Systematic review

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Abstract

The importance of selective and stepwise caries removal techniques versus complete caries removal is supported by evidence. However, no recent systematic review is available to determine the best technique. Thus, this study's objective was to review the comparative evaluation of clinical, radiographic, and restorative success of selective (SCR), stepwise (SWR), and complete caries removal (CCR) in deep dentinal caries in primary teeth. The data was extracted and critically analyzed through an electronic search of various databases from 2012 to 2024 by two independent investigators, articles were first selected by reading the titles and abstracts, duplicates were removed. Full texts of the selected articles were read and databases were screened for any remaining relevant articles and were analysed by two reviewers for final eligibility. Seven articles met the inclusion criteria, and their data was transformed in the form of tables by two authors, along with assessment of quality of included articles. Database sources included PubMed, Google Scholar, Cochrane, and EMBASE. RCT's on pediatric patients under 12 years of age with deep dentinal caries in a primary molars comparing one caries removal strategy (SCR, SWR, CCR) with another and recording outcomes such as pulp exposure, clinical and radiographic success after a follow-up period of more than four months, were selected. Based on the studies, SCR and SWR may result in a lower risk of pulp exposure but a higher rate of restorative failure compared to CCR. The risk of bias among the articles revealed 1 (low risk), 3 (some concerns), and 3 (high risk). More randomized controlled trials (RCTs) with lower risk of bias are necessary to make a definitive selection between these techniques.

Keywords- deep caries, selective caries removal, stepwise caries removal, complete caries removal.

I. Introduction

Dental caries, an infectious disease that degrades tooth structure¹, affects 60–90% of school-aged children, according to the WHO². Despite advancements in dietary counseling and dental hygiene, 50% of children still require treatment.³

Various techniques have been developed to manage carious lesions, particularly in primary molars.² Traditionally, the approach involves complete removal of all affected structures, which can be distressing for children, leading to anxiety and poor cooperation.²

Recent understanding of the caries process and the potential for remineralization has led to development of less invasive methods² such as selective caries removal (SCR) and stepwise caries removal (SWR), moving away from the traditional "extension for prevention" approach.⁴⁻⁵ These techniques focus on maintaining pulpal health and leveraging the reparative capabilities of the pulp-dentine complex.⁶

SCR involves selectively removing soft carious dentin from the pulpal wall while completely excavating caries from the lateral walls until reaching sound dentin. A protective liner, such as calcium hydroxide, is applied, followed by a permanent restoration like glass ionomer cement (GIC).⁷ This approach helps limit bacterial access to carbohydrates, promoting a favorable environment for remineralization and halting caries progression.⁸

In contrast, SWR entails partial caries excavation initially to stimulate mineral deposition, followed by a second excavation step after a delay. While selective and total caries removal (TCR) techniques are recommended for permanent teeth, there is a lack of research comparing these methods specifically for primary teeth.⁹

Despite evidence supporting SCR, many practitioners still favor more invasive techniques, expressing concerns about the impact of retaining soft dentin, on restoration adherence and overall treatment efficacy.¹⁰ Three systematic reviews have compared SCR, SWR, and TCR methods, but the most recent evidence has yet to be incorporated into clinical practice.

This systematic review (SR) aims to evaluate the effectiveness of SCR and SWR versus TCR in terms of clinical, radiographic, and restorative failure for managing deep dentinal caries in pediatric patients under 12 years old. The goal is to provide a clearer understanding of the best practices for treating deep caries in primary teeth.

II. Materials And Methods

D) PROTOCOL AND REGISTRATION-

This systematic review aims to evaluate the comparative clinical, radiographic, and restorative failures, as well as the risk of pulp exposure, in SCR, SWR, and CCR strategies for deep dentinal caries management in primary teeth.

This systematic review was registered in PROSPERO under the reference number CRD42024543229 and was conducted as per PRISMA guidelines (Figure 1).

Fig 1- Prisma flow diagram

II) INFORMATION SOURCE-

An electronic search was conducted through databases like PubMed, EMBASE, Cochrane, Google Scholar from 2012 to 2024 by two independent investigators.

III) SEARCH STRATEGY-

"Primary teeth"(MeSH Term) AND "Complete caries removal" OR "Primary teeth" AND "Stepwise caries removal" OR "Primary teeth" AND "Selective caries removal" OR "Primary teeth" AND "Selective caries removal" AND "Complete caries removal". Two reviewers assessed abstracts and full texts for inclusion criteria. To avoid bias opinion of third party was obtained.

IV) STUDY SELECTION-

-Inclusion criteria-

1. Patients under 12 years.
2. Deep dental caries with no history of spontaneous pain, swelling, fistula, and mobility in deciduous teeth.
3. Studies comparing SCR and SWR with CCR.
4. Studies recording pulp exposure, clinical, radiographic and restorative failure with follow up of >4 months.
5. Randomized control trials.

-Exclusion criteria-

1. Studies involving children requiring special care.
2. Studies with any radiographic signs indicating pulpal necrosis.
3. Studies conducted under conscious sedation or general anesthesia (GA).
4. Papers available as abstracts only.

IV) DATA COLLECTION PROCESS-

Data was carefully extracted from the studies using a standardized extraction form by two authors, focusing on key points (Tables 1,2).

V) QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF THE STUDIES

The quality of included studies varied, with particular weaknesses noted in user involvement, theoretical frameworks, sample size estimation, and reliability of measurement tools as presented below: (Table 1)

Table 1 – Mean score (Standard deviation and range) for each quality criteria against which the papers were assessed.

Table 1-Quality Criteria	Mean Score (SD, Range)
Evidence of user involvement in design	0.5 (0.2, 0-2)
Explicit theoretical framework	0.9 (0.5, 0-2)
Evidence of sample size considered in terms of analysis	2.1 (1.4, 0-3)
Statistical assessment of reliability and validity of measurement tools	1.8 (0.9, 1-3)
Strength and limitations critically discussed	1.3 (0.8, 0-3)
Good justification for method of analysis	2.3 (1.4, 0-3)
Clear description of research setting	2.0 (1.7, 1-3)
Description of procedure for data collection	1.9 (1.3, 1-3)
Statement of aims/objectives in body of report	2.2 (1.4, 1-3)
Detailed recruitment data	2.3 (1.6, 1-3)
Representative sample of reasonable size	2.1 (0.9, 1-3)
Rationale for choice of data collection tool	2.0 (1.1, 1-3)
Fit between research question and method of analysis	2.5 (1.2, 1-3)
Fit between research question and method of data analysis	2.3 (1.2, 1-3)

III. Results

I) Study selection

A comprehensive search across multiple databases identified 1,260 articles. The primary search yielded 1,180 studies, with 80 excluded for reasons such as incomplete blinding and selective reporting. Of the 80 papers reviewed, 73 were irrelevant, leaving 7 clinical trial publications that met the criteria.

II) Description of the Studies

1. **Phonghanyudh et al. (2012, Thailand)**¹¹ evaluated GIC restoration outcomes in 6-11-year-old children, comparing CCR and PCR, showed 2,1 pulp exposures, 2,0 clinical/radiographic failures and 10,15 restorative failures after 12 months
2. **Franzon et al. (2014-2015, Brazil)**¹²⁻¹³ compared survival rates of composite restorations after PCR and TCR in 3-8-year-olds, showed 15,1 pulp exposures, 2,5 clinical/radiographic failures and 8,20 restorative failures after 24 months.
3. **Mello et al. (2018, Brazil)**¹⁴ focused on pulp exposure and restorative failures after SCR and CCR in 5-9-year-olds, showed 13,0 pulp exposures, 0,0 clinical/radiographic failures and 2,1 restorative failures after 4-6 months.
4. **Elhennawy et al. (2018, Germany)**¹⁵ compared SCR and SWR in 3-9-year-olds. SCR, SWR showed 0,2 pulp exposures, 1,0 clinical/radiographic failures and 0,0 restorative failures after 12 months.
5. **Libermana et al. (2019, Brazil)**⁹ assessed the survival of restorations after SCR and TCR in 3-8-year-olds, showed 1,15 pulp exposures, 3,1 clinical/radiographic failures and 3,1 restorative failures after 36 months.
6. **Pereira et al. (2020, Brazil)**¹⁶ evaluated pulp vitality in children after NSCR versus SCR showed 3, 2 pulp exposure, 3,5 clinical/radiographic failures, 29,26 restorative failures after 33 months.

7. **Elhennawy et al. (2021, Germany)**¹⁷ compared SCR and SWR in 3-9-year-olds, showed 0,2 pulp exposure, 2,2 clinical/radiographic failures, 8,7 restorative failures after 24 months. (Table 3,4)

Table 3 Sr.no	Authors, Country, Year of publication	Journal	Study design, Follow-up Sample size calculation Unit of randomization	Teeth (participants: age)	Lesion extension	Treatment (used instrument)	Control (used instruments)
1.	Phonghanyudh et al ¹¹ 2012 Thailand	Community Dental Health	Parallel group 12 mo SSC: Yes UR: child	276 (276:6-11 y)	Caries > 1/3 dentin	SCR only at EDJ (nt0 = 92) (n12M = 89) -SCR (nt0 = 92) (n12M = 89) (hand excavator)	CCR (nt0 = 92) (n12M = 88) (bur)
2.	Franzon et al ¹²⁻¹³ 2014-15 Brazil	Caries Research	Parallel group 24 mo SSC: Yes UR: tooth	124 (51:3-8 y)	Caries > 3/4 dentin	SCR (nt0 = 67) (n24M = 66) (bur)	CCR (nt0 = 57) (n24M = 54) (bur, hand excavator)
3.	Mello et al ¹⁴ 2018 Brazil	Int. J Clin Pediatric Dent	Parallel group 4-6 mo SSC: Yes UR: tooth	62 (44:5-9 y)	Caries > 2/3 dentin	SCR (nt0 = 24) (n4-6M = 17) (bur)	CCR (nt0 = 25+13) (n4-6M = 19) (bur, hand excavator)
4.	Elhennawy et al ¹⁵ 2018 Germany	Journal of Dentistry	Parallel group 12 mo SSC: Yes UR: child	74 (74:3-9 y)	Caries > 2/3 dentin	SCR (nt0 = 37) (n12M = 36) (bur)	SWR (nt0 = 37) (n12M = 36) (bur)
5.	Liberman et al ⁹ 2019 Brazil	Journal of Dentistry	Parallel group 36 mo SSC: Yes UR: tooth	124(51:3-8 y)	Caries > 3/4 dentin	SCR (nt0 = 65) (n36M = 64) (bur)	TCR (nt0 = 55) (n36M = 52) (bur)
6.	Pereira et al ¹⁶ 2020 Brazil	Caries Research	Parallel group 33 mo SSC: Yes UR: tooth	278 (117: 4-8 y)	Caries ≥1/2 dentin	SCR (nt0 = 141) (n33M = 141) (bur,hand excavator)	NSCR (nt0 = 137) (n33M = 137) (bur)
7.	Elhennawy et al ¹⁷ 2021 Germany	Clinical Oral Investigations	Parallel group 24 mo SSC: Yes UR: child	74 (74:3-9 y)	Caries > 2/3 dentin	SCR (nt0 = 37) (n24M = 31) (bur)	SWR (nt0 = 37) (n24M = 32) (bur)

III) RISK OF BIAS ASSESSMENT

The risk of bias was assessed using the Revised Cochrane Risk-of-Bias (ROB) Tool for Randomized Trials by three authors independently. Key findings include: (Table 2)

- Low ROB in the oldest study.
- Concerns regarding randomization and allocation in some studies.
- High risks with blinding and incomplete data in others.

Table 2- Studies (year)	Randomization process	Allocation concealment	Blinding of participants & Personnel	Blinding of outcome	Incomplete outcome data	Selective reporting	Other Bias
Phonghanyudh et al 2012	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Franzon et al 2014	?	?	+	+	?	+	?
Mello et al 2018	+	+	-	+	+	-	+
Elhennawy et al 2018	+	?	?	+	-	+	+
Liberman et al	+	+	+	-	?	+	?

Table 2- Cochrane risk of bias assessment

2019							
Pereira et al 2020							
Elhennawy et al 2021							

+/green color: low ROB

?/yellow color: some concerns;

-/red color: high ROB

Table 4- PROTOCOL	RESULTS		
	OUTCOME SCR	SWR	CCR
1.Contamination control: no Liner: no Restorative material: GIC ¹¹	Pulp exposure 1 Clinical/radiographic failures NA Restorative failures (Frencken criteria) 15	NA 2 NA 10	2 0
2.Contamination control: rubber dam Liner: calcium hydroxide Restorative material: composite resin ¹²⁻¹³	Pulp exposure 1 Clinical/radiographic failures 5 Restorative failures (USPHS criteria) 20	NA NA NA 8	15 2
3.Contamination control: no Liner: calcium hydroxide Restorative material: resin-modified GIC ¹⁴	Pulp exposure 0 Clinical failures 0 Radiographic failures 1	NA NA NA 2	13 0
4.Contamination control: cotton rolls Liner: no Restorative material: Compomer ¹⁵	Pulp exposure 0 Clinical/radiographic failures 1 Restorative failures (USPHS criteria) 0	2 0 0 NA	NA NA NA
5.Contamination control: Rubber dam Liner: calcium hydroxide Restorative material: composite resin ⁹	Pulp exposure 1 Clinical/radiographic failures 3 Restorative failures (USPHS criteria) 3	NA NA NA 1	15 1
6.Contamination control: Rubber dam Liner: calcium hydroxide Restorative material: composite resin ¹⁶	Pulp exposure 2 Clinical/radiographic failures 5 Restorative failures (USPHS criteria) 26	NA NA NA 29	3 3
7.Contamination control: cotton rolls Liner: no Restorative material: Compomer ¹⁷	Pulp exposure 0 Clinical/radiographic failures 2 Restorative failures (USPHS criteria) 8	2 2 7	NA NA NA

IV. Discussion

For the management of deep caries, it is essential to understand the available treatment options. The decision on which technique to employ should be based on evidence, analyzing the most favorable outcomes in terms of clinical, radiographic, and restorative success rates.

Selective versus complete caries removal

Schwendicke et al⁸ found PCR to be more beneficial than full excavation. According to Ricketts et al¹⁸ partial excavation decreased the rate of pulp exposure. Franzon et al¹²⁻¹³ reported that PCR is a minimally invasive method for treating primary teeth and that pulp vitality is not affected by the retention of carious dentin. Mello et al¹⁴ found that PCR and TCR had success rates of 94.2 and 89.6%. Liberman et al⁹ showed restorations after SCR had a 3.44 times higher likelihood of failing than restorations carried out after TCR. Pedrotti DDS et al¹⁹ indicated that the likelihood of restorative failure in primary teeth may increase with selective excision of fragile dentin-carious tissue. Elody Aiem et al²⁰ demonstrated a lower risk of pulp exposure following SCR or SWR. Santamaria et al²¹ suggested that less invasive caries therapies including selective or no caries removal are preferable to CCR. Hamouda et al²² also found a lower risk of pulp exposure following SCR.

Stepwise versus complete caries removal

Magusson et al²³ found that compared to TCR, SWR demonstrated lower risks of pulp exposure. Orhan et al²⁴ reported a significant decrease in bacterial growth during treatment stages of the two-visit IPT. Phonghayudh et al¹¹ showed that rates of GIC restoration and pulp survival did not differ statistically between two groups. Schwendicke et al⁸ found SWR to be more beneficial than full excavation. Ricketts et al¹⁸ observed no difference in the risk of restoration failure or symptoms of pulp disease, and noted that SWR decreased the rate of pulp exposure. Bjorndal et al²⁵ found higher success rates with SWR (60.2%) compared to NSCR (46.3%), with SWR showing significantly prolonged pulp vitality. Elody Aiem et al¹⁰ indicated that the risk of clinical or radiographic failure related to pulpo-periodontal problems remained unchanged. Compared to CCR, SWR may result in a lower risk of pulp exposure. Hamouda et al²² also found a lower risk of pulp exposure following SWR.

Selective versus Stepwise caries removal

Maltz et al²⁶ found success rates of 56% for SWR and 80% for PCR group. Compared to SWR, PCR dramatically decreased the incidence of pulp necrosis. Elhennawy et al¹⁷ reported that the restoration integrity was satisfactory in both groups. In comparison to selective excavation (SE), SWR incurred considerably higher treatment and opportunity costs. After two years, SE and SWR demonstrated comparable efficacy.

Regarding the shortcomings of this systematic review (SR), we note the lack of research contrasting SWR and CCR, as well as SCR and SWT. To determine whether SCR can be widely applied or is suitable only in specific circumstances, further subgroup analyses are needed. These should focus on cooperative versus uncooperative children, different age groups, varying depths of carious lesions, and the types of restorations (occlusal and approximal) using different materials.⁵ Extended monitoring, as indicated in three RCTs^{8,13,16,17} will help identify the optimal caries removal methods for individual primary tooth cases.

V. Conclusion

Recommendations for caries removal techniques do not necessarily apply to primary teeth; however, the risk of pulp exposure was significantly decreased with SCR and SWR compared to CCR. To establish the routine efficacy of SCR, which is already recommended for permanent teeth, more RCTs with greater statistical power are needed.

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